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0.1	5.10.2020	Marko Savolainen (VTT)	Draft structure based on H2020 DMP template
0.2	17.11.2020	Marko Savolainen (VTT)	Version for consortium review
1.0	27.11.2020	Marko Savolainen (VTT) Jan Stip (OPT/NET)	Reviewed version to be published

1. Executive summary

The Goldeneye project combines information from different remote sensing and positioning technologies to collect high-resolution data of the mine. The project exploits Earth observation and Earth GNSS satellite positioning data together with data collected with drone-based and ground-based proximity sensors to be used in efficient exploration, extraction and closure of the mine. These tools generated in this project will be demonstrated in five field trials in Germany, Bulgaria, Romania, Kosovo and Finland, creating a compelling value proposition for implementation across the mining industry value chain. The project has a duration of 3 years and is funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement number 869398. The consortium include a large industrial partner, 7 SMEs, 4 academic/research centres and 4 end-users, supported by a strong advisory board of experts in geosciences.

2. Introduction

This report is the deliverable D8.7 of the Work package 8: "Exploitation & Scaling Up" of the GOLDENEYE-project. This Data Management Plan (DMP) provides an overview of the datasets and file types to be collected or generated during the project span and defines the GOLDENEYE consortium's data management policy that is used with regard to these datasets.

3. Data summary

The Goldeneye project will implement a unique combination of remote sensing and positioning technologies, exploiting Earth observation and Earth GNSS data, together with data fusion and processing powered by data analytics and machine-learning algorithms. The data is collected and gathered into Golden AI platform, which combines the information from satellites, drones and in-situ sensors and converts the information into actionable intelligence for safety, environmental monitoring and overall productivity. Data analytic methods and machine-learning algorithms are used to process the data and transfer the information into easily understandable form. Data is processed and converted into actionable intelligence for safety, environmental monitoring and overall productivity. Golden AI platform is described in more detail in openly available deliverable of the GoldenEye project: "*Data acquisition and processing initial report*" (D1.1).

This is the first version of the data management plan, and reflects the current view of the equipment and data types needed in the project. This document is updated during the course of the project. It may be, that during the project new equipment are introduced to provide data to the platform. However, the data types of those possible new instruments most likely fall into the data categories listed in this document.

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Figure 1 shows the main data sources of GoldenEye project: satellites, drone-based and ground-based sensors. These are described in great detail in deliverable D1.1 openly available in Zenodo repository.

Figure 1: main data sources of GoldenEye project, Golden AI platform and applications

3.1. Satellite based data

The Goldeneye project will enable novel uses of Earth observation and Earth GNSS data in the mining industry:

- The project will use Copernicus and other contributing mission data for precise surface change detection regardless of cloud cover and time of the day.
- The project will use interferometric SAR (InSAR) Level 1 SLC data combined with Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and Surface Elevation Models (SEM) obtained from LIDAR instruments. Appendix B
- Using super-resolution and data fusion technologies, we will get the global scale and temporal resolution of the Copernicus program as well as the necessary details required for monitoring of mines. Chapter 2.5
- The project will use several Copernicus Data and Information Access Services (DIAS) and regional Copernicus partner hubs as well as other cloud providers hosting satellite data, benefiting from the Sentinel Hub's federation.
- Project will use VHR data from Copernicus contributing missions and potentially partner missions of NASA, JAXA and several commercial supplies in case these provide unique value and hyperspectral data (bridging gaps in European EoD portfolio).

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3.2. Drone based data

In comparison to satellite imagery, airborne sensors (deployed in drones) have a high spectral resolution and they can offer remote operational mapping of secondary surface mineralogy, as surrogates to the mapping of acid drainage-related distributions of polluting heavy metals and indicators of stress in the local vegetation. Pre-dawn thermal scanning from drones can detect and monitor subsurface fires, identify concealed mineshafts and map the extent of near-surface workings.

The drones used in GoldenEye project are equipped with RGB cameras, thermal cameras, multispectral cameras and electromagnetic (EM) sensors.

3.3. Ground based sensor data

In recent decade different handheld and portable technologies have raised interest in the mining industry as they could provide information in real-time and would not cause delays in exploration and extraction surveys. One of the objectives of the Goldeneye project is to study the use of portable Raman spectroscopic analyser and Active Hyperspectral Spectrometer for mineral exploration and thus detection of valuable and secondary minerals in the mining sites. Beak will also apply portable XRF devices during the ground survey in the Erzgebirge test site. Geochemical analyses will be conducted for collected rock samples by University of Sofia in Bulgaria. Beak will do it in the Erzgebirge.

3.4. Data formats

Common output product and exchange data file type in GoldenEye project is GeoTIFF. Majority of satellite data and data from drone instruments are stored in GeoTIFF format. This is useful file format in the project, since it allows georeferencing information to be stored in tiff image metadata. TIFF stands for *Tagged Image File Format* and is commonly used raster graphic file type. The digital elevation models (DEMs) are one example of information stored in geoTIFF files. DEM GeoTIFF associates z-coordinate for every (x,y) coordinate and includes the Coordinate Reference System (CRS) so that it is possible to relate these pixel coordinates to real world coordinates.

The raw data from acquired from the drone sensors is in tiff or jpg image format but is further processed to be in geotiff format for the RGB, EM and multispectral maps (orthomosaics). 3D models generated in the project are in the standard dxf and psx file formats. The estimated size of the drone data is 300 Gigabytes per square kilometer (Gb/km²). With the current plan of test flights and data acquisition to be performed, the total amount of data generated in the project with drones will be around 100 Gb.

Ground based sensors include Raman instruments. The data generated are spectra i.e., wavelengths and corresponding sensor signals stored in an array. In case of multiple spectra measured with same device, it is not necessary to store the wavelength values multiple times as shown in Table 1. In the table, a1 corresponds to spectrum 1 value with wavelength w1 and so on.

Table 1

Wavelength	w1	w2	w3	w4	w5	w6	w7	...
Spectrum 1	a1	a2	a3	a4	a5	a6	a7	...
Spectrum 2	b1	b2	b3	b4	b5	b6	b7	...
Spectrum 3	c1	c2	c3	c4	c5	c6	c7	...

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CSV file format is a file format for storing data of many kinds, also spectroscopic data. As it is an open file format, it is a good format to store open spectral data in GoldenEye project. CSV stands for *Comma-Separated values*, and each row in file represent a data record (spectrum in this case). Numerous file types are used in spectroscopy, but all the spectral data to be openly accessible in a GoldenEye repository will be preferably in CSV file format or other easily operable format like ENVI.

Table 2 lists the data types used in the project planned at this stage. This table is updated from deliverable 1.3.

Table 2: Data types and formats related to project applications

Application	Data types	Data formats	Geo-reference
Multi- and hyperspectral satellite data processing (various)	Spectral data	SAFE, ENVI	WGS84:UTM
SAR satellite data (S1, TSX or equivalent)	IW, SLC Level-1 product, SM - TSX	SAFE, ENVI , CoSAR	WGS84:UTM
RGB imaging with drones	VIS spectral data	8-bit RGB GeoTiff (orthomosaics) tiff/jpeg (raw images)	WGS84:UTM RTK GPS positioning
Thermal Imaging with Drones	Thermal spectral data	16-bit Geotiff (orthomosaics) tiff/rjpeg (raw images)	WGS84:UTM GPS positioning
MS imaging with Drones	Multispectral data	16-bit Geotiff (orthomosaics) tiff (raw images)	WGS84:UTM GPS positioning
EM sensing with drones	EM data for xy-spatial matrix	esri-ascii grid, geosoft grdgrid	WGS84:UTM RTK GPS positioning
Elevation sensing with drones	Image matrix where pixel values indicate height	8-bit RGB (pseudocolor) GeoTiff (orthomosaics)	WGS84:UTM RTK GPS positioning
RAMAN prototype development - Mobile device	Spectral data: Raman shift, 532 nm EX WL. Spatial data in X-Y for areas of interest	.csv and .txt files	<u>WGS84:UTM, ERTS 1989 datum with UTM Zone 33N projection</u>
RAMAN prototype development - Drilling device	Spectral data: Raman shift, 532 nm EX WL	.csv and .txt files	WGS84:UTM
Active hyperspectral prototype development	Spectral data: 1.9-2.45 μm , 100 channels, spatial data in X-Y with min. 1 cm step	tdms database file, .geotiff raster files	WGS84:UTM

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GNSS/GPS indoor navigation	3D location	N/A or GPS signals*	WGS84:UTM
GNSS/GPS outdoor navigation	3D location	NMEA	WGS84:UTM
Platform for use cases	Input data in OGC, CEOS ARD (CARDL) or de-facto popular standard formats. Outputs data in OGC compliant visualisation maps	Multiple formats such as COGTiff, SAFE, CoSAR, ENVI, CARDL Euro Data cubes. API: S3 COS Access protocols: SCP, sFTP, NFS.	WGS84:UTM

pXRF data will be stored in Beak's SQL database and can be exported from there as XLS or CSV files. Coordinates will be stored in WGS84.

4. Data management policy

4.1. Making data findable

All open data, results and publications produced in the GoldenEye will be made findable by adding file type specific metadata, by using persistent Uniform Resource Locators and by assigning **Digital Object Identifier (DOI)** so that the material can be easily cited. DOIs can be only given by DOI registrants through DOI registration agency. As the open material in the project will be deposited in Open Access repository **Zenodo**, it will be assigned a DOI automatically. If it seen necessary to deposit material to other locations (for example institutional repositories, web pages etc.), at least the material will be identifiable by persistent URI.

4.2. Data file naming conventions

By default, the filenames used in project's data files are of the form:

{place}_{data modality}_{sensor band}_{date}_{file identifier}.{file extension}

For example in case of an RGB image generated by drone camera:

trePCA_drone_RGB_20201210_003.tif

Datasets that are obtained as such or it is beneficial to use a standard naming convention like RINEX in case of GNSS data, can be named using such convention for clarity.

4.2. Search keywords

All open GoldenEye material and results deposited in a repository will have associated search keywords and metadata. Keywords are chosen from controlled vocabularies specific for the datatype, whenever possible.

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4.2. Version numbering

Version numbering will be applied to all material that is updated during the project. In Zenodo repository, the DOI versioning is in use and it is possible to update datasets after publishing and cite a specific version or all versions of a dataset.

4.3. Metadata

The common file type in satellite data and many applications in GoldenEye project is **geoTIFF**. It uses a public domain metadata standard, allowing georeferencing information to be stored in the TIFF file. It contains information about coordinate reference system (CRS) of the data. This is a beneficial file type in the project since geolocation is an essential parameter in the Golden AI platform.

With the metadata tags of geoTIFF tile, it is possible to describe the actual real world location that each pixel of the image represents. The tags include *coordinate systems, ellipsoids and geoids, datums and projection*.

Although CSV has been a very popular file type for a long time, the problem has been the lack of metadata standard and the fact that file format doesn't allow metadata directly to the file. To overcome this problem in GoldenEye project, separate files containing the metadata is used according to newly developed CSVW standard. *CSV on the Web (CSVW)* is a still developing standard for metadata descriptions for tabular data. CSVW Namespace Vocabulary Terms is listed in the web page <https://www.w3.org/ns/csvw>. CSVW metadata is captured in .csv-metadata.json files that are shared with the CSV files that they describe. As an example, a CSV file called data.csv and its metadata data.csv-metadata.json will be shared in Zenodo repository as a file pair named

data.csv

data.csv-metadata.json.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- The terms "European Union (EU)" and "Horizon 2020"
- The name of the action, acronym and grant number
- The publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- A persistent identifier.

4.3. Making data openly accessible

As written in Grant agreement, unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must disseminate its **results** by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means, including scientific publications (in any medium). However, this does change the obligation to protect the results, confidentiality and security obligations, or obligations to protect personal data, as described in Articles 27, 36, 37 and 39.

Publication of data is formally agreed via an email to data management responsible from authorised person from each partner. The list of authorised persons is stored in project's shared folder in Teams.

As mentioned in the GA, Section 2.2.6:

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The consortium will voluntarily participate in the Open Data Pilot. Data management activities are part of task 8.5 and will start with the formal release of a Data Management Plan (D8.5.1) at M6 and a Data Management Report (D8.5.2) at M36. The project will follow the open data management guidelines of the H2020 Programme:

- The project will deposit the research data in a research data repository that facilitates linking publications and underlying data through persistent identifiers and data citations.
- The project will take to enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) this research data by attaching Creative Commons Licenses to the data deposited
- The project will provide information via the research repository about the tools available to the users that are needed to evaluate the results (e.g. statistical models, data exchange formats), and if they are open source, will provide these instruments.

All peer-reviewed scientific **publications** related to project results are given open access by default, free of charge for any user. More specifically, at the latest on publication, an electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication is deposited in a repository for scientific publications (for example Arxiv.org).

An open access to deposited publication is ensured via repository immediately on publication if an electronic version is available free of charge. In any other case, the open access will be ensured within six months of publication. This open access will be provided in this project by publishing only in **gold open access journals** or otherwise openly accessible journals. In addition, access to the bibliographic metadata is given an open access via the repository.

The research **data** needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publication is also deposited to the repository. This is to be done preferably at the same time as the electronic copy is deposited to the repository.

Deliverables that are marked 'public' in the grant agreement will be shared openly in the repository as soon as possible after they are accepted by the consortium. These deliverables and their due dates in months are listed Table 3.

Table 3: Public deliverables of GoldenEye project.

Deliverable number	Deliverable title	Type	Due date (months)
D1.1	Data acquisition and processing initial report	Report	4
D1.3	High-level architecture design report	Report	6
D8.7	Data management plan	Report	6
D2.1	EOD acquisition report	Report	18
D7.2	Communication report 1	Report	18
D7.5	Dissemination report 1	Report	18
D5.1	Data integration framework	Demonstrator	18
D3.4	Telemetry and flight automation report	Report	22

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D5.3	Safety, geo-hazard and environmental monitoring application toolkit	Demonstrator	28
D5.4	Other operational application toolkit	Demonstrator	29
D7.7	Community outreach report	Report	34
D7.8	Collaboration report	Report	34
D8.6	Industrialization report	Report	34
D7.3	Communication report 2	Report	36
D7.6	Dissemination report 2	Report	36
D8.4	Impact analysis report	Report	36
D8.8	Data management report	Report	36
D6.7	Public summary and evaluation of the field trials	Report	36
D8.9	Open repository store	Open research data pilot	36

All open material of the project (data, associated metadata, documentation and code) will be accessible at an Open Access repository as soon as possible after its generation. The repository for GoldenEye data is chosen to be **Zenodo** (www.zenodo.org), a CERN based repository launched in 2013. There is a community page for GoldenEye project accessed from the web page

(<https://zenodo.org/communities/goldeneye-h2020>).

Data that is not public can be archived to the repository using a restricted access method. There is no need of data access committee in the project.

Accessing Zenodo repository and GoldenEye community page containing the data requires only web browser. Open data and publications can be accessed without logging in to the repository. Uploading of files and accessing the restricted content requires login to the repository and permissions can be given to selected users. Metadata is harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol and open API's can be used to access data (for example REST API).

Documentation describing the data and how to view it is provided with the data. Some file formats, for example csv file format, are in text format. They can be opened in any text editor or with excel in case of csv file. ENVI file is an example of a binary file format that needs a specific viewer to interpret the data. The file formats that can be opened with open source software are primarily used.

There exists free viewers to open many file types, including geoTIFF file format. GeoTIFF, as an example, can also be opened programmatically by using for example free R programming language. If there exist a (viewer) program or open source code having a license that allow distribution of the (viewer) software in Zenodo repository, this is preferably done. In any case, a suggestion of the program(s) to be used in viewing data is given in the data-related documentation.

4.4. Making data interoperable

The open data to be shared is interoperable by preferably having file types that are in either in ASCII file form, can be opened with free viewers, or with open source programs like python or R.

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For the numerical analyses (in FLAC 2D) e.g. there is a batch file (with the extension .dat) that can be read with the Notepad or Notepad++. These files can be loaded and re-called in the FLAC commando interface by the viewer and so will get the geometry and the data parameters for e.g. of the 2D model.

There are no restrictions on the use of the open published data, but users are required to acknowledge the Consortium and the source of data in the possible resulting publications. Common data vocabularies, standards and methodologies are to be used in order to ensure interoperability of the data.

In case it is necessary to generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, mappings to more commonly used ontologies are provided.

4.5. Data re-use and licenses

The data will be openly available under CC0 Creative Commons license and is accessible also with open APIS (like REST). Metadata is exported via OAI-PMH and can be harvested.

The open data is available in the repository as soon as possible after its generation, except for the cases that there is a decision to secure the intellectual property with patents. In such cases, Zenodo allows data to be deposited under embargo status so that repository restrict access until the end of embargo period.

The open data produced in the GoldenEye project has an unlimited access for third parties and there will not be a time limit for the re-usability of the data or other open material.

4.6. Data quality assurance

The project will have mechanisms for quality assurance in the project, as is *A Project Quality Handbook* developed by VTT.

Data quality is assured by careful characterisation of the measurement set-ups and validation of the data. Multiple measurements and data sources are used whenever possible.

5. Allocation of resources

5.1. Costs for making data FAIR

The Zenodo repository services are free of charge, including data archiving with associated DOIs. Copyright licensing is also free of charge with Creative Commons.

Costs related to gold open access for peer-reviewed publications are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant and is included in the project partner's budget. Project web page is also one channel for project related

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information has been budgeted for the website related costs. Data, however is not stored in the project web page.

5.2. Data management responsible

Marko Savolainen will lead the coordination of the updates to the data management plan. He will also be responsible for organizing data backup and storage, data archiving and for depositing the data to Zenodo repository.

5.3. Resources for long term preservation

The value and need for long term public data preservation and related resources will be determined during the progress of the project.

6. Data security

Data security in Zenodo repository is at high level. Data centres are located on CERN premises with restricted access. All access to zenodo.org happens over HTTPS and there is a network attack detection system. Zenodo stores user passwords using strong cryptographic password hashing algorithms.

Each file deposited to Zenodo has two replicas located on different disk servers. There are two independent checksums for each file, which enables automatic detection and recovery of data corruption on disks. Zenodo saves backups containing metadata and persistent identifiers in every 12 hours and backups are stored in tape storage once a week.

7. Ethical and legal aspects

GoldenEye partners will follow the EU and national standards regarding ethics and data management. Article 34 of the Grant Agreement sets ethics and research integrity obligations that partners will follow.

In addition there is a work package (WP10) in the project for setting out the 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with. Deliverable D12.4 will have a thorough analysis of the ethics issues raised by this project and the measures that will be taken to ensure compliance with the ethics standards of H2020.

8. Other issues

There are no other issues.

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